

SEVENTH UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT ASSEMBLY (UNEA-7)

Nairobi, Kenya | 8–12 December 2025

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The seventh United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA-7) in December 2025, delivered a Ministerial Declaration, eleven resolutions, and a series of institutional decisions providing guidance on UNEP's programmes, financial and trust fund arrangements, and the organizational framework for UNEA-8.

While UNEA-7 delivered formal outputs, these largely reflected institutional continuity rather than substantive political breakthroughs, continuing the pattern seen in UNEA-6. Earlier sessions, such as UNEA-4 and UNEA-5, had exhibited stronger political dynamics and a slightly more ambitious agenda-setting, but UNEA-7 focused on what was broadly acceptable, emphasizing consensus and operational continuity over transformative action.

The Assembly avoided or discarded its most politically sensitive and high ambition files. Consequently, most proposals implying the development of new binding commitments, substantial financial obligations, or transformative regulatory frameworks struggled to reach consensus. This led to them either being postponed or softened. The outcome can be explained by the role played by certain groups, persistent geopolitical tensions, rising international insecurity, and diverging development priorities.

Overall, UNEA-7 points to a model of environmental multilateralism characterized by what could be called consolidation or stagnation, achieving institutional continuity at the cost of political ambition.

Despite its institutional resilience and the engagement of its Member States, the Assembly's international polarization together with the insistence on consensus-based decision-making considerably limits its ability to advance on substantial issues. Progress therefore was incremental but not transformative, with ambition restricted by political and economic realities.

When looking at the upcoming UNEA-8 in December 2027, certain implications stand out. First, an even stronger necessity for early agenda-setting and coalition-building to effectively tackle politically complex issues. Second, more emphasis toward the implementation of existing mandates rather than the creation of new ones, which risks further limiting the ambition and relevancy of environmental multilateralism. Through this, UNEA is in danger of consolidating a model that is procedurally stable but ineffective and misaligned with the urgency of the accelerating triple environmental crisis.

II. UNEA-7 in 2025: Context and constraints

i. The geopolitical background

UNEA-7 took place against a backdrop of disputed multilateralism, characterized by a growing skepticism toward the role of international institutions and the increasing fragmentation of global governance and order. Major geopolitical tensions and ongoing conflicts or rivalries continued to affect trust levels among Member States, narrowing the space for compromise and effective long-term cooperation. In this context, environmental negotiations were inevitably impacted by broader foreign policy considerations rather than treated as isolated multilateral processes.

These structural constraints were clearly manifest in the consensus-based dynamics of UNEA-7. **While consensus—in line with overall UN traditions—is central to the Assembly’s legitimacy and inclusiveness, it creates a persistent risk that final outcomes reflect only the lowest common denominator and do not fully match the urgency and level of ambition required.** Accordingly, negotiations at UNEA-7 often involved progressive weakening of language, the use of non-binding formulations, or the elimination or postponement of some ambitious, yet contentious, elements.

Furthermore, the negotiations were shaped by procedural considerations, mainly disputes over mandates, scope, as well as potential institutional overlap. Many Member States remained sensitive to any perceived expansion of UNEP’s authority or perceived duplication with binding multilateral environmental agreements (MEA), such as the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

Finance emerged as a recurrent fault line, with hot topics (such as, for example, funding sources and obligations, burden-sharing, and the voluntary nature of contributions versus pre-established contributions) repeatedly shaping negotiations.

UNEA’S CONSENSUS PRACTICE THUS CONTINUES TO FAVOR INCREMENTAL PROGRESS (IF ANY) AND POLITICAL SIGNALING OVER TRANSFORMATIVE COMMITMENTS.

While this approach ensures unity and institutional stability, it also limits the UNEP’s ability to deliver rapid or ambitious responses to accelerating environmental challenges.

UNEA-7 reaffirmed this dynamic: As a forum, it remains essential for setting agendas and coordinating efforts, but its ability to spur bold collective action is increasingly limited by geopolitical and economic pressures. In practice, this has transformed consensus from a tool for collective ownership and legitimacy into a constraint that systematically filters out ambition before it even reaches the negotiating table. As a result, topics where delay is directly translated into environmental harm, such as in the form of pollution exposure or ecosystem degradation, are precisely those most likely to be deferred.

ii. How these constraints typically show up at UNEA

Most political and economic constraints at UNEA show up through the way decisions are made and negotiated. **UNEA works by consensus, which often leads to watered-down outcomes with proposals adjusted to the lowest level in order for the most reluctant countries to accept.** Ambitious ideas are frequently softened or delayed.

Process becomes a matter of tactics and substance goes to the background as the attention and priorities shift. Furthermore, there is widely agreed reluctance on giving UNEA a stronger role. This refusal is justified by the argued need to avoid overlaps with other UN bodies and even international agreements. This position is often expressed by rising concerns regarding “mandate creep.” As a consequence, the Assembly limits decisions, often avoiding specificity.

Finally, persistent and unresolved disagreements continue to impede progress, particularly with respect to financing. **Divergent positions on who should bear financial responsibility, the scale of contributions, and the appropriate mechanisms for delivering funds remain a central fault line in negotiations.** As a result, many countries are reluctant to accept commitments that could entail new or expanded financial obligations in the absence of clear and predictable funding arrangements.

Because decisions are taken by consensus, UNEA is considered very effective at building political legitimacy. However, this same decision-making system tends to limit its ability to drive transformative action. **The need for universal agreement tends to favor incremental steps, general language, and process-oriented outcomes over strong commitments or binding measures.**

III. Outcome package at a glance: What was adopted

While **15 draft resolutions and 3 draft decisions were initially tabled by Member States for UNEA-7**, not all were adopted, underscoring the Assembly’s emphasis on convergence and consensus-building.

The negotiation process followed a staged approach for each draft. An initial set of draft texts was tabled before and during the session, covering a wide range of thematic and procedural issues. Subsequently, these drafts were organized by topic to pave the way for the negotiations, reducing potential duplications and overlaps.

Through several successive rounds of informal consultations and revisions, the number of texts was progressively narrowed. **Drafts that failed to attract sufficient cross-regional support or that raised unresolved political or financial concerns were either merged into broader texts, scaled back, or set aside.**

This process resulted in a smaller group of more mature texts: those considered politically capable of securing consensus. Therefore, the final outcome package reflects not the full range of initial ambitions but only those proposals that could be viable within UNEA’s consensus-based framework, particularly contracting areas related to finance, governance reform, and norm-setting.

i. **Headline outputs of UNEA-7**

The outcomes of UNEA-7 can be hierarchically grouped into three complementary layers, each playing a distinct role in the Assembly's institutional architecture:

Ministerial Declaration: At the highest level, the ministerial declaration is used as a shared political statement by ministers. While not legally binding, it expresses common priorities, frames key environmental challenges in political terms, and compromises to collective commitment. The declaration is used as an agenda-setting indicator, helping to set the direction for future work and highlighting areas of convergence, and reaffirms UNEA's position as the leading global forum for environmental policy.

Resolutions: Typically proposed by sponsoring countries or coalitions, resolutions may form the backbone of UNEA's policy contribution, giving substance and effect to political commitments. While they are non-binding, sponsors play a central role in shaping language, assigning follow-up tasks to UNEP and other relevant actors, and shaping the work programmes and partnerships.

Decisions: These focus on the practical and institutional side of UNEA's work, decisions address governance, administrative, and programme-related issues, including budgeting, oversight, or operational arrangements. While more technical than resolutions, decisions are essential for implementation, as they determine how mandates are financed, managed, and monitored.

While the ministerial declaration is developed and consulted under the auspices of the UNEA presidency, the resolutions and decisions are proposed by sponsoring countries or coalitions.

The ministerial declaration was developed and negotiated primarily through Presidency-led intergovernmental consultations, with the UNEA-7 Presidency (Oman) acting as penholder, circulating successive drafts (zero/ first/ final/ revised final) and running an iterative consultation process to build broad ownership. Sponsors of resolutions draft the texts, negotiate the necessary amendments, and guide them through the Assembly, playing a key role in shaping language, and influencing broader outcomes, while the drafts of the three decisions were prepared and submitted by the UNEP secretariat. Both were negotiated among member states and (together with the final text of the ministerial declaration) formally adopted by the Assembly, signaling consensus on strategic priorities and intergovernmental cooperation, even if they are not legally binding.

Taken together, these three layers both illustrate and devise UNEA's dual function as a political platform for agenda-setting and a governing body responsible for steering and supervising the UN environment system.

A key scientific anchor was the launch of GEO-7 (Global Environment Outlook 7), UNEP's landmark report released at the closing plenary.¹

Titled "A Future We Choose," it is considered one of the world's most authoritative assessments of environmental trends, evaluating progress toward SDGs and UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement goals while analysing contrasting 2050 pathways. It describes a "business-as-usual" trajectory of intensifying crises versus sustainable options blending technological efficiency, reduced consumption, and policy shifts to avoid irreversible thresholds and unlock trillions in global benefits.

¹ [United Nations Environment Programme. 2025. *Global Environment Outlook 7: A Future We Choose – Why Investing in Earth Now Can Lead to a Trillion-Dollar Benefit for All*. Nairobi: UNEP.](#)

ii. Thematic clustering of the adopted resolutions

The following table provides an overview of the resolutions adopted at UNEA-7, grouped by five thematic clusters. For each cluster, it indicates the number of resolutions adopted, summarizes their core focus, and explains their broader political and institutional significance.

Thematic cluster	Number of resolutions within each cluster	What does it do?	Why does it matter?
Nature and blue Planet	3 out of 11	It addresses ecosystem-based challenges such as coral reef protection, marine biomass proliferation and glacier loss, largely through cooperation, assessment, and support to both national and regional action	It shows continued political attention to climate-linked ecosystem impacts, while remaining within non-normative and limited implementation approaches
Pollution, chemicals, and waste	3 out of 11	It advances policy guidance on pollution, chemicals, waste management, and related human health and environmental risks, often reinforcing existing frameworks and UNEP programmes	It reinforces UNEA's traditional strength and continuity in pollution governance, even if ambition is regarded as moderate compared to moments such as UNEA-5.2
Risk and resilience	2 out of 11	It focuses on environmental dimensions of risk, readiness, and response, mainly including wildfires and ecosystem resilience, and emphasizing early warning, and knowledge exchange	It reflects growing concern with climate-driven risks, framing UNEP's role around preparedness rather than a crisis response authority
Governance and synergies	1 out of 11	It encourages cooperation, coordination, and information-sharing across environmental institutions and processes	It both recognizes fragmentation in environmental governance and also the political sensitivity around any institutional reform
Emerging themes	2 out of 11	It explores new or cross-cutting issues such as the environmental dimensions of artificial intelligence and antimicrobial resistance, primarily through assessments, mapping both exercises, and dialogue	It shows UNEA's intention to contribute to an agenda of innovation, while keeping these new topics firmly in the exploratory and non-regulatory space

Table 1: Distribution and significance of adopted resolutions at UNEA-7.

IV. Actors, coalitions, and observable behaviors

This section attempts to analyse the main behavioral patterns in the UNEA-7 negotiations and how multilateral dynamics shaped outcomes. The focus is on political behavior: Which actors pushed for stronger outcomes, which resisted, and how those interactions affected the final package.

i. Observable patterns

This subsection identifies recurring negotiation behaviors that reveal critical points in multilateral cooperation. Each pattern can be structured through a general perspective on what the pattern looks like in practice, a functional approach regarding who typically uses it, and a result analysis of its impact on ambition, timing, and substance.

Dissociation or distancing from outcomes

Certain delegations expressed reservations or clarified that some outcomes did not fully reflect their positions. This occurred even in cases in which they had contributed to an outcome, allowing adoption by consensus. Such reservations tend to weaken political ownership of the texts and reduce the normative force of the agreed package.

These instances include closing remarks made with emphasis on language on Means of Implementation (MoI), finance, and specific commitments that could not be fully accepted. **A major player—the US—was even largely absent from negotiations, only to dissociate itself from the outcome in the final plenary.** Furthermore, civil society and some major groups also highlighted concerns that outcomes fell short and lacked substantive ambition, signalling a gap between adopted text and broader advocacy expectations.

This disengagement limits how confidently the package can be presented as a politically unified signal and indicates that fractures remain even within consensus. **Not only impacting the text's legitimacy, decisions adopted by consensus but publicly disowned by key actors also carry limited political weight and are less likely to translate into implementation or follow-up at national level.**

Procedural contestation and time pressure

Although the Assembly formally met from 8–12 December, the time available for substantive negotiations was far shorter. **Much of the opening period was taken up by procedural matters and general debates, leaving roughly a two and a half day deadline for delegates to complete a very ambitious agenda.** This created what was described as a pressure cooker and led negotiators to raise procedural arguments. Those arguments include working hours, sequencing of draft texts, and consensus norms. At the end, debates over extending sessions or adopting “take it or leave it” approaches consumed both political capital and time.

There were concerns raised on procedural matters by some parties. Right after the opening ceremony, once the Committee of the Whole (CoW) was established, regional groupings called for a limitation on parallel sessions and late-night meetings. Those late discussions risked non-attendance or ineffective participation from smaller delegations. Furthermore, several delegations opposed “take it or leave it” approaches, suggesting alternative ways forward through clearer rules for extending contact group time.

Procedural contestation heightened time pressure and encouraged conservative drafting. It led to the postponement of substantive disagreements to plenary, and favored safe and general language over specific and innovative commitments. **At the end, time pressure consistently advantaged those actors seeking to delay, dilute, or avoid commitments, while penalizing those pushing for specificity or innovation such as Tuvalu or Vanuatu’s delegations.**

Mandate overlap objections and institutional boundary-setting

Multiple delegations resisted proposals perceived as exceeding UNEP’s mandate, especially regarding references to other UN bodies or to obtaining broader environmental governance roles.

The procedural deadlock was most severe regarding the Medium-Term Strategy (MTS) and Budget associated with its Programme of Work (PoW),² where disagreements over UNEP’s institutional reach led to an “existential” impasse that threatened the organization’s future operation.

Similar objections dominated in debates regarding environmental crime and other governance themes, where some delegations insisted on limiting language in order not to further expand UNEP’s institutional reach. This coalition represents a significant shift of power in environmental multilateralism, moving toward a coordinated defense of institutional boundaries. Their primary motivation was the fear of UNEP gaining power to authorise further action by the UN Security Council or the Human Rights Council.³

By reinforcing UNEA’s role as a coordinating and advisory body rather than an environmental authority, this defensive coalition partially resets the ceiling of ambition. It ensures any governance oriented outcomes remain non-normative independently of the severity of the environmental risks.

Strategic withdrawals by sponsors to avoid weak outcomes

Some actors chose to pull or defer proposals that were likely to be adopted only in a heavily diluted form.⁴ In the face of the Assembly’s resistance, Vanuatu withdrew, recognizing that consensus could not be achieved on the text. Similarly, drafts on environmental crime were not adopted, partly because certain representatives preferred withdrawal over a significantly weakened package.

² *United Nations Environment Programme. 2025. [UNEP’s 2026–2027 Programme of Work \(PoW\)](#).*

³ *Third World Network. [TWN Info Service on Biodiversity and Traditional Knowledge \(Dec25/05\): UNEA-7 reaffirms Rio principles, advances global environmental action](#), 19 December 2025.*

⁴ *United Nations Environment Programme. [UNEA-7 Draft Resolutions: Active Protection of Deep-Sea Ecosystems \(UNEP/EA.7/L.8\). Draft Resolutions and Decisions Submitted for Consideration at the Seventh Session of the United Nations Environment Assembly \(UNEA-7\), Nairobi, Kenya, 8–12 December 2025.](#)*

ii. Dynamics of negotiation and the risk to UNEA’s impact

For the negotiation outcome to be understood the different narratives and the patterns of alliance must be considered. These dynamics have shaped both scope and ambition of the final package, and were reflected in the objectives and narratives of the main negotiating blocs. The negotiation patterns observed carry important implications for the credibility of the Assembly, including not only the agreed outcomes of the negotiations but also the prospects for meaningful progress and future sessions. Over time, if the current gap between formal agreement and action broadens, UNEA’s credibility as a forum capable of responding to the accelerating triple environmental crises will likely further erode.

The persistent reliance on lowest-common-denominator consensus is no longer a neutral procedural feature of the Assembly but a substantive risk to UNEA’s credibility.

WHEN AMBITION IS SYSTEMATICALLY DILUTED TO SECURE UNANIMITY, UNEA OUTCOMES RISK BECOMING POLITICALLY SYMBOLIC RATHER THAN OPERATIONALLY MEANINGFUL.

By affecting legitimacy and reducing UNEA’s output authority, the system raises doubts about how seriously the commitments reached can be taken.

Furthermore, procedural contestation, mandate sensitivity, and financial disagreements affect both outcomes and implementation. When outcomes are narrowly framed in order to secure consensus, follow-up action tends to be cautious and generally uneven. Language lacking clarity may lead to diffused responsibilities across institutions and resource distribution. **This further increases the gap between real impact and political agreements, limiting UNEA’s ability to drive sustained and effective action and its impact on partner organisations.**

These dynamics suggest that, without any substantial adjustments, UNEA will continue to face constraints on ambition in future sessions. Strategic withdrawals and narrowed mandates may preserve political space in the short term, but they indicate growing reluctance to use the Assembly for collective decisions, which leads to an individual conceptualization of the fight to stop the environmental crisis.

The challenge for UNEA-8 (2027) will be whether Member States can move beyond defensive consensus-building toward more decisive, better-resourced outcomes that can match the scale of environmental challenges.

Photo credit: UNEP/Kiara Worth

V. What fell away

i. What was withdrawn or not adopted

This section examines the main proposals that did not survive the UNEA-7 negotiation process. Taken together, these withdrawals or extinguished texts demonstrate that the Assembly's limits were not accidental, transitory, or simply technical, but indeed represent political and structural issues:

Politically sensitive norm-setting

As mentioned in the section before, drafts attempting to advance or strengthen new normative concepts encountered significant resistance. Topics such as environmental crime, liability, or accountability proved to be highly sensitive items on the agenda. The primary opponents argued that these topics fall outside UNEP's scope or mandate. These Member States utilized the consensus-based system as a "de facto veto" to prevent what they termed "mandate creep." Concerns centered mostly on the potential legal implications, sovereignty, and the fear of creating *de facto* obligations through UNEA language. The underlying motivation for this group was largely tactical: They sought to protect national sovereignty and prevent the securitization of environmental issues, specifically fearing that UNEP language could empower the UN organs such as the Security Council or the Human Rights Council to interfere in domestic affairs. In several cases, sponsors faced pressure to dilute ambition or abandon texts altogether, leading to withdrawal rather than adoption of weakened outcomes.

Mandate overlap and institutional turf

Due to strong emphasis on institutional boundaries, mandate integrity, and a reluctance to expand UNEA's scope of activities, those proposals touching on issues governed by existing international institutions or processes were frequently challenged on mandate grounds. **Consistent with patterns observed in politically sensitive norm-setting, several negotiating groupings were particularly reluctant concerning any perceived intrusion on parallel treaties or more specialized bodies.** While framed as a necessary limit to avoid duplication, their rejection systematically blocked critical discussions such as marine biodiversity and ocean governance.

Touching upon mandate overlap and institutional turf, concerns were expressed building on the lack of clarity regarding MoI. Some delegations emphasized that the creation of new mandates would lead to a burden increase on developing nations without the provision of the key resources to meet them, creating empty or unfair commitments. These delegations traded ambition for institutional realism, which led to emphasising UNEP's role as coordinating rather than regulatory authority. This may be considered a deliberate strategy of accepting the narrowing of the scope but protecting the existing negotiation space and its implementation. **In summary, the focus on UNEP's institutional mandate creates a persistent tension between Member States seeking to expand its authority and those determined to preserve the current governance framework.**

Governance, headquarters, and institutional reforms

As manifested by the group profiling, reaching agreements regarding governance arrangement, institutional reforms or headquarters issues proved to be nearly impossible. **Strong divisions led to what was described as an “existential deadlock” over the MTS 2026-2029 and the Programme of Work and Budget with both documents becoming the main battleground for broader geopolitical conflicts.** Ultimately, the lack of political space and time together with the refusal to move away from their “individual barricaded positions” meant that many governance-related proposals were either dropped, postponed or significantly narrowed to ensure the basic operational continuity of the organisation.

ii. The “negotiation delta” method

While only what was achieved will have a real impact, what could have been and was not is also meaningful. **Through the “negotiation delta” method, this brief attempts to show what was lost, diluted, or reshaped during negotiations, rather than only noting whether a text was adopted or not.** It compares early drafts with final outcomes to reveal how political constraints translated into concrete changes:

Scope

Several early drafts framed environmental challenges in broad terms, proposing comprehensive approaches or addressing issues at a global scale. As negotiations progressed, these ambitions were often narrowed, shifting from broad policy frameworks to more limited thematic focus, voluntary initiatives, or information-sharing activities. For example, proposals initially intended to address governance gaps or global environmental risks were reframed to focus on mapping existing efforts, sharing best practices, or further assessments.

Institutional tasking and follow-up

While some initial drafts conferred explicit tasks to the UNEP, final texts scaled back. Those functions, including for example the preparations of substantive outputs and organizing expert processes or structural follow-up, were often substituted by report requests, consultations, inventory, or even simply deferred to future sessions. Finally, the language scale-back not only reduces momentum between the sessions but reflects a limited appetite for expanding UNEP’s functional role.

Strength of language

One of the clearest downgrading of the negotiations was the operative language. Early formulations using verbs such as “decides,” “requests,” or “urges” were frequently replaced by verbs such as “encourages,” “invites,” or “notes” in proposals like the ones regarding sound management of chemicals and waste or mineral circularity. While it may be argued that language is secondary as UNEA outcomes are non-binding, politically these shifts are remarkable. The use of stronger language would have signaled clearer expectations for action by the UNEP itself or its members and partners. Soft language clearly reflects a tendency for flexibility and discretions, particularly on sensitive topics.

Finance

This proved to be one of the main impediments and quarrels across the negotiations, especially in nature- and climate-related drafts. Most references in early drafts to additional or new resources were removed or softened, with final outcomes tending to rely on already existing resources, voluntary contributions, or future collection of funds.

The clear avoidance of concrete financial arrangements reflects long-standing divisions over financial responsibility and burden-sharing, and it significantly limits the likelihood that more ambitious aspects of the outcomes will be implemented.

Timelines and reporting

The necessity of clear timelines and reporting requirements were also a frequent matter of discussion and a constant element on the negotiation table.

While draft proposals often included specific reporting deadlines, final texts tended to adopt extended or open-ended timeframes. In some cases, mandatory reporting obligations were softened into optional updates or “general progress reporting” as appropriate.

Time and bargaining bandwidth constraints

As a result of time pressure, growing negotiation fatigue, prioritization of adoptable or viable outcomes and limited negotiating capacity, several proposals, despite not being rejected on substance, were in fact withdrawn. Furthermore, time struggles led to concurrent late-night sessions and parallel informal discussion, limiting the impact of small and personnel-limited delegations.

As attention focused on a smaller set of priority texts, less mature or more complex or disputed drafts were sidelined. Actors sometimes opted strategically to leave aside proposals, judging that the necessary negotiation was no longer feasible within the available time. The use of the consensus-based approach as a de facto veto, especially during the last hours, kept some sensitive issues off the table as delegates knew that reopening balanced compromises or deadlock issues would consume the remaining scarce negotiation time.

iii. Common patterns of change at UNEA-7

Looking across the outcome package, several consistent patterns emerge in how draft texts have evolved during negotiations.

THE MOST COMMON PATTERN WAS A GRADUAL DOWNSHIFTING OF AMBITION AS TEXTS MOVED TOWARD ADOPTION.

Operative language was frequently softened, reducing political expectations and signaling growing caution, particularly on issues with legal, economic, or governance implications.

Furthermore, scope was also narrowed with a draft addressing comprehensive topics often reframed to focus on specific themes, voluntary actions, or preparatory steps such as assessments and exchanges of best practices. References to finance followed a similar trajectory with most initial texts pointing to new or additional resources being scaled back or removed, replaced by references to existing funds or voluntary contributions.

Across multiple resolutions, responsibility was increasingly diffused, with a rise in formulations and phrasing inviting rather than instructing actors to engage. This shifts responsibility from UNEA-7 and its members to stakeholders, minimizing political and institutional risk while preserving consensus.

Simultaneously, negotiations did not lead to a weakening of texts by default. In several cases, ambition was traded for greater procedural clarity. This can be seen in the development of reporting requests, which most resolutions contain in their final form. Furthermore, proposals that were closely anchored in existing UNEP programmes tended to survive negotiation in a more comprehensive form. **The new activities embedded within established workstreams reduced the concerns regarding mandate expansion and led to texts while being less transformative and more institutionally grounded.**

Photo credit: UNEP/Kiara Worth

Case A: Handling novelty: Artificial intelligence and antimicrobial resistance

The environmental dimensions of artificial intelligence and antimicrobial resistance illustrate how UNEA handles novelty, in this case on aspects of technology and health. The Assembly proved willing to engage in discussions in both cases. However, this engagement was limited by carefully designed boundaries, with language avoiding any prescriptive character on its approaches and emphasizing UNEP's role in supporting dialogue and contributing environmental perspectives to broader international debates. **Therefore, we can argue that novelty seems to be accepted as long as it focuses on exploratory and non-normative outcomes.**

Case B: Withdrawn files: Coordination among multilateral environmental agreements

By contrast, the withdrawal of proposals addressing coordination and collaboration among multilateral environmental agreements points at the shortcomings of consensus. **Despite its underlying objective (improving coherence across the environmental landscape) being widely acknowledged, the draft faced unease due to mandate overlaps and reform arguments.** Faced with the prospect of a heavy dilution, sponsors ultimately decided to withdraw the proposal. This example illustrates a clear boundary UNEA seems to be unable to modify or overcome. While it may encourage cooperation, any effort perceived as reshaping institutional relationships or reallocating the relevant authority remains highly controversial, and consequentially, politically out of reach.

Case C: Stagnation through managed continuity: Mineral and metals governance

Unlike emerging issues such as artificial intelligence or withdrawn proposals that exceed political tolerance, minerals and metals represent a long-standing environmental challenge linked to supply chains, energy transitions, and development models discussed in the agenda for years. However, despite its relevance, UNEA-7 commitments brought simply incremental coordination and reaffirmed existing approaches.

While the resolution briefly acknowledges the environmental and social impacts of mineral extraction and processing as largely demanded by Colombia (the sponsor of the proposal), it deliberately avoids contentious dimensions such as binding sustainability standards, or demand reduction strategies. The outcome reflects a delicate political balance shaped by competing economic interests. North-South asymmetries and sensitivities regarding resource management led to an impasse on stronger normative guidance and ambition regarding multilateral discussions on the subject. As a consequence, the sponsors (Colombia and Oman) retained a narrow and non-prescriptive text, emphasising information-sharing, voluntary cooperation, and national capacity-building in order to secure consensus.

In this sense, minerals and metals governance at UNEA-7 illustrates not a lack of awareness, but a political choice to prioritize consensus over engagement with the environmental implications of extractive action. While the outcome maintains mineral governance on the agenda, it is kept only in politically tolerable bounds for all countries, abandoning any transformative element. Therefore, although the issue is placed on the agenda, the Assembly's outcomes reflect a strategy of postponement rather than resolution.

VI. UNEA-7 compared with UNEA-4, UNEA-5, and UNEA-6

UNEA-7 forms part of a longer institutional trajectory rather than a discrete turning point.

To assess whether the Assembly's role is expanding or contracting, this section compares UNEA-7 with previous sessions, focusing on function and political effect rather than the mere volume of adopted outputs.

A useful point of comparison is the Assembly's uneven success at launching major new global processes.

Discussions on plastic pollution have been present on the UNEA agenda since UNEA-2 in 2016, where the issue was formally introduced and gradually accumulated political momentum across successive sessions. However, it was only at UNEA-5.2 in 2022 that Member States crossed the necessary political threshold to mandate the establishment of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee (INC) on plastic pollution. This decision, together with progress on the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Panel on Chemicals, Waste, and Pollution (ISP-CWP), makes UNEA-5.2 stand out as a session that successfully translated prolonged agenda-setting into concrete institutional follow-up.

Earlier sessions, including UNEA-4, contributed to awareness-raising and thematic consolidation but stopped short of launching a standing global negotiating process.

Against this backdrop, the handling of minerals and metals governance at UNEA-7 illustrates a contrasting dynamic.

Despite the long-standing recognition of the environmental, economic, and geopolitical significance of mineral extraction (particularly in the context of energy transition), UNEA-7 did not succeed in initiating a comparable intergovernmental process.

While the issue was formally addressed, the adopted resolution remained narrowly framed, emphasizing voluntary cooperation, information-sharing, and capacity-building while carefully avoiding any move toward structured global governance, normative guidance, or negotiating mandates. Unlike plastics at UNEA-5.2, minerals and metals did not cross the political acceptability threshold required to shift from agenda presence to process creation, underscoring UNEA's limited capacity to act where environmental ambition intersects directly with strategic resources, development models, and industrial policy.

UNEA-7 presents itself as a partial continuation of UNEA-6, which adopted a relatively large number of resolutions across diverse themes such as minerals, pesticides, and land degradation, but did not launch any new global processes or negotiating tracks.⁵

UNEA-7 followed a similar pattern. While it adopted texts touching on metals governance, artificial intelligence, and antimicrobial resistance, these outcomes primarily reiterated existing approaches or mandated further assessment and coordination. **Whether this constitutes genuine and real progress remains questionable as final texts are weak, non-operational, and explicitly non-prescriptive, reinforcing existing strategies rather than transformative governance.**

With respect to implementation architecture, UNEA-7 adopted the MTS 2026–2029 and the Programme of Work and Budget for 2026–2027.⁶ Formally, these documents provide strategic orientation for UNEP and signal a continued emphasis on implementation.

⁵ United Nations Environment Programme. [Outcomes of UNEA-6](#).

⁶ United Nations Environment Programme. ["UNEA-7 Charts a Path Toward a Resilient Planet."](#)

Substantively, however, their adoption was marked by difficult and, at times, non-cooperative negotiations, and the final texts largely reaffirm existing priorities rather than introducing new mechanisms or expanding UNEP's functional role.

In this sense, UNEA-7 shows a clear prioritization of institutional alignment and political feasibility over environmental ambitions, purposely consolidating a constrained and voluntary framework rather than the proactive strengthening of countries' implementation capacity.

As in previous sessions, finance and MoI were a pivotal discussion item. Despite the emphasis on the Ministerial Declaration and several resolutions on the extreme urgency of addressing the triple planetary crisis, UNEA-7 outcomes avoided calling for significant financial commitments or new funding arrangements.

The discussions highlighted the persistent gap between political recognition of environmental crises and the willingness to mobilize resources.

Compared with UNEA-5.2, where the launch of negotiating processes signalled readiness for future institutional development, UNEA-7 remained firmly within the bounds of voluntary and existing frameworks.⁷

Finally, UNEA-7's agenda reflected a broad thematic spread, combining already established priorities such as pollution, chemicals, and ecosystem resilience with emerging cross-cutting issues including artificial intelligence and antimicrobial resistance. Compared to UNEA-6's explicit framing around the triple planetary crisis, UNEA-7 devoted greater space to these emerging themes. However, following the general governance trends, engagement with the new topics focused sharply on assessment, dialogue, and coordination rather than normative guidance or regulatory ambition. Furthermore, it frames an expansion without the corresponding development of institutional or political capacity and instruments to act. Consequently, compared to earlier sessions, UNEA-7 does not mark an expansion of environmental multilateralism but rather its consolidation within increasingly narrow political boundaries.

Key comparative observations

- Ambition has been traded for a lowest-common-denominator consensus. The outcomes of UNEA-7 satisfied the most reluctant parties rather than the most ambitious ones. Proposals for the development of new multilateral commitments or transformative regulatory frameworks were systematically watered down or postponed and the outcome package, while politically acceptable, suggests a tactical shift that replaced ambition by "institutional realism" and operational continuity.
- Unlike UNEA-5.2, which launched the INC on plastic pollution, UNEA-7 failed to launch any meaningful new global negotiating tracks. While the Assembly addressed emerging themes like minerals, metals, and artificial intelligence, these were kept strictly within a non-regulatory space, consolidating the Assembly as a coordination forum focused on assessments and voluntary cooperation instead of a legislative and authoritative body.

⁷ See *United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA), Ministerial Declaration of the 2019 United Nations Environment Assembly: Innovative Solutions for Environmental Challenges and Sustainable Consumption and Production*, UNEP/EA.4/HLS.1 (Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme, 2019); and *United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA), Ministerial Declaration of the United Nations Environment Assembly at its Fifth Session: Strengthening Actions for Nature to Achieve the Sustainable Development Goals*, UNEP/EA.5/HLS.1 (Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme, 2022).

- Persistent arguments regarding mandate creep and institutional duplication have led the Assembly to a deliberate institutional rollback. While earlier sessions expanded UNEA's institutional role, specific delegations groups consistently objected to any expansion or expansive interpretation of UNEP's mandate and authority.
- There has been a reduction in the appetite for institution-building as a reaction to rising skepticism towards international organizations. Due to broader foreign policy considerations and geopolitical rivalries, independent environmental processes were halted by a consensus-based system. The geopolitical context, together with tight time limits and barricaded positions, led to a general language and limited changes.

VII. Overall assessment: What UNEA-7 tells us about environmental multilateralism

UNEA-7 offers a revealing close-up picture of the state of environmental multilateralism at a moment marked by heightened geopolitical tension, fiscal constraints, and institutional disagreements. Instead of making a breakthrough or initiating a reversal, the session shows a recalibration of environmental multilateralism away from ambitious objectives and towards—at best—consolidation.

National interests such as energy politics, fiscal priorities, and sovereignty claims are increasingly shaping negotiation dynamics underneath the official agenda. This phenomenon resulted from multiple dynamics, including countries distancing themselves from negotiations and final outcomes, deliberate efforts to constrain ambition by weakening negotiated language, and resistance to governance reform.

As a consequence of the negotiation dynamics, the Assembly's outcomes have moved away from expansive norm-setting. The outcome package and the issues that fell away all point to a system that remains active and relevant, but is increasingly constrained in how ambition is expressed, delivered, and implemented.

UNEA still performs an agenda-setting role, which is consistent with its self-depiction as the world's highest-level environmental forum. The breadth of issues addressed at UNEA-7, from pollution and ecosystem protection to artificial intelligence and antimicrobial resistance, stresses its power and political visibility. Yet agenda-setting alone cannot ensure downstream delivery.

The outcomes of UNEA-7 emphasize reporting over action and confirm that the Assembly currently lacks the authority to drive implementation beyond voluntary alignment. Rather than acting as a normative body attempting to launch new global processes, UNEA-7 acted as a coordination forum, focused on aligning priorities, encouraging cooperation, and mandating assessments within clear and existing institutional boundaries (e.g., resolution on chemicals and waste management).

WHILE THIS APPROACH DOES NOT DIMINISH ITS RELEVANCE *PER SE*, IT DOES NARROW THE SPACE IN WHICH IT CAN DELIVER TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE.

The expanding environmental agenda was curtailed during the session by the Assembly's capacity to negotiate by consensus. **While Member States were willing to place a wide range of topics on the table, negotiations repeatedly converged on narrower scopes, softer language, and postponement of actions and follow-up.** The result was an outcome package that, while thematically rich, is poor in operative outcomes. This is manifested in the shift from proposals for structured MEA coordination to "encourage information-sharing" as well as the lack of new funding commitments and the reliance on existing and voluntary resources. **This suggests that agenda expansion is not matched by a corresponding increase in negotiation width, raising questions about how much UNEA can realistically absorb and undertake without diluting ambition.**

The session also highlighted the persistent challenge of governance fragmentation in the global environmental landscape. Many resolutions acknowledged the need for coherence and coordination across multilateral environmental agreements and other related processes. **Yet every attempt to move beyond encouragement and information-sharing, and create more structured forms of coordination, proved to be too ambitious due to its political sensitivity for certain delegations.** Opposition was mainly led by a small group of highly influential actors, all of whom counteracted proposals of strengthening UNEP's coordinating authority or creating cross-cutting governance structures.

Their concerns regarding possible impacts on sovereignty, energy policy autonomy, or institutional influence led to the withdrawal or dilution of governance-focused proposals (e.g., governance reform under the "special session on MEA coordination" or resolutions on planetary boundaries). Therefore, the clear rejection of these proposals indicates that, despite the wide endorsement of the underlying problem, efforts that touch on institutional authority or mandate quickly encounter resistance.

THROUGHOUT THE OUTCOME PACKAGE, IMPLEMENTATION WAS APPROACHED CAUTIOUSLY, AND UNEP WORK WAS OFTEN FRAMED AROUND REPORTING, ASSESSMENT, OR FACILITATION RATHER THAN ACTION.

Furthermore, timelines were frequently extended or left open-ended while references to finance were restrained, relying on existing resources and voluntary contributions. This can be seen as a pragmatic acknowledgment of capacity constraints but also raises concerns about follow-up. **UNEA-7 outcomes are generally realistic in what they ask institutions to do, yet this realism comes at the cost of limited impact.** It must be noted that this form of institutional realism may be indeed normalising low environmental ambitions and condition UNEP's capacity to act in the long term.

To sum up, UNEA-7 serves as an indication that environmental multilateralism is not failing due to a lack of expertise or space within the policy agenda, but rather due to political unwillingness to translate shared concerns about urgent matters into multilateral processes where national or regional action will not be sufficient in view of the establishment of collective obligations.

VIII. Outlook to UNEA-8 (December 2027)

UNEA-7 did not close debates so much as it paused or reshaped them. Therefore, several issues remain unresolved or were only partially addressed by the resolutions. This makes it highly likely for them to return at UNEA-8 for further discussion.

How and with what strength these issues may re-emerge depends on political appetite, sponsorship dynamics, and the broader geopolitical context in which negotiations unfold.

i. Likely carry-overs to UNEA-8

Questions around coherence and coordination across MEAs are unlikely to disappear. While UNEA-7 confirmed the political sensitivity of these discussions, it also revealed a broad recognition of fragmentation in the global environmental architecture. Future proposals may shift further toward technical cooperation, joint reporting, or informal coordination mechanisms, as observed at UNEA-7, in order to advance without triggering resistance and reopening fundamental mandate debates. These dynamics mirror ongoing debates around the restructuring of the UN and the challenges put forward by shrinking resources, which directly constrain the capacity of both UNEP and other UN entities to expand mandates or undertake large-scale coordination initiatives.

Debates around environmental crime, including ecocide-type framings, are similarly likely to re-emerge, albeit cautiously. UNEA-7 showed that, in this specific area, its appetite for strong norm-setting was limited. However, growing public and political attention may encourage sponsors to test certain policy entry points, such as capacity-building or information-sharing programmes.

Marine and ocean-related topics, such as deep-sea ecosystems and cross-cutting ocean governance, are expected to remain prominent in future environmental debates. Standing at a crossroads between biodiversity, climate change, and economic interests, they continue to attract political attention. This attention is expected to translate into science-based approaches and negotiable or voluntary mechanisms rather than broader governance reform.

Finally, the newest topics introduced at UNEA-7, especially the environmental implications of artificial intelligence and antimicrobial resistance, are now firmly on the table and ready to be taken further. **Having cleared the initial obstacle of agenda inclusion, these issues may return in a more concrete form, moving from assessment toward structuring, guidance, or integration into the UNEP programme.**

ii. Three scenarios for UNEA-8

Based on the dynamics at UNEA-7, **three broad scenarios can be envisaged for UNEA-8**. These are not predictions, but plausible pathways shaped by current trends.

Scenario 1: “Consolidation”

Under this scenario, UNEA-8 and future sessions would focus primarily on implementation. Outcomes would emphasize follow-up, reporting, and alignment with already existing mandates rather than new initiatives. While the agenda would remain wide, negotiations would prioritize deliverability and institutional realism, avoiding transformative or controversial proposals. This would entail reinforcing UNEA’s coordination role while simultaneously consolidating its limited political signaling. While politically manageable, this scenario risks locking UNEA into a cycle of reporting without impact.

Scenario 2: “Selective breakthroughs”

In this scenario, UNEA-8 would deliver one or two high-profile outcomes while remaining cautious on most other fronts. Any breakthroughs would likely be tightly scoped, backed by strong sponsorship, and carefully framed to avoid mandate conflicts. The areas most likely to see concrete proposals include oceans, pollution, or more mature emerging themes such as AI, echoing the UNEA-5.2 experience but on a more selective scale. This could help rebalance how UNEA’s ambition and political impact are perceived. This scenario would require deliberate political investment and coalition-building well before UNEA-8 rather than reliance on last-minute consensus.

Scenario 3: “Fragmentation”

A less favourable scenario would be one of growing fragmentation, with more draft resolutions being withdrawn or significantly watered down, more frequent dissociations, and outcomes increasingly reduced to minimal consensus language. Formal agreement would still be reached, but the political signal would be weakened, and UNEA’s credibility as a forum for setting collective direction and a global environmental agenda could be undermined or even hijacked. Under this scenario, UNEA could retain its formal legitimacy but would risk losing its ability to effectively shape collective environmental direction.

Organizational profile

SLYCAN Trust is a non-profit think tank working on climate change, sustainable development, climate finance, risk management, entrepreneurship, biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, security, and social justice including gender and youth empowerment. Our work spans the national, regional, and global level from policy analysis and evidence-based research to capacity-building, technical support provision, and on-the-ground implementation.

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